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Effect of Dividend Policy on the Firms Performance of Firms Listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange

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Abstract

The dividend policy of a company plays a pivotal role in shaping dividend distribution decisions, with management guiding the allocation of profits to shareholders through dividends. These policies are globally implemented to establish standardized guidelines for specific firms, bolster credibility, and instill shareholder confidence. While both local and international studies have delved into the intricate link between dividend policies and firm performance, their outcomes have yielded inconclusive results. Nevertheless, scholars have particularly emphasized the influence of payout and reinvestment on these policies. In this context, the present study sought to investigate the impact of dividend policy on firm performance by scrutinizing entities listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. This research was grounded in well-established theories like Agency theory, signaling theory, and dividend irrelevance theory, while the research design seamlessly aligned with the research question and problem. Employing a descriptive research design, the study aimed to unravel the relationship between variables. The target population consisted of NSE-listed companies, totaling 63 firms across the 2018-2022 timeframe, furnishing an ample dataset for comprehensive insights. Secondary data was meticulously drawn from the NSE handbook and the PAFS, focusing on financial statements mandated by the Capital Markets Authority (CMA). Collected data underwent a rigorous process of review, classification, coding, and analysis using the user-friendly SPSS software, known for handling intricate data with ease. The presentation and interpretation of findings involved a blend of inferential and descriptive statistics. The model summary revealed an R-value of 0.755, signifying a substantial 75.5% correlation among the examined variables. The R-Square value further clarified that 57.1% of the variations in firm performance, concerning dividend policy for NSE-listed firms, could be attributed to firm size, company earnings, leverage, and firm performance itself. The remaining 42.9% of fluctuations stemmed from unaccounted factors. ANOVA results validated the model's statistical significance, with a significance value of 0.000 well below the P-Value threshold of 0.05. Utilizing unstandardized coefficients in column B to formulate the mathematical model, it was revealed that the collective impact of predictor variables on firm performance stood at 0.155. The findings also unveiled that firm size maintained a positive and noteworthy correlation with firm performance ($\beta=0.006$; $p=0.036 < 0.05$). Further exploration highlighted that company earnings exhibited an adverse and substantial connection with Firm Performance (regressed variable) ($\beta=-0.098$; $p=0.000 < 0.05$). Additionally, the data in section 4.7 illuminated leverage's positive and material link with firm performance, as demonstrated by ($\beta=0.094$; $p=0.000 < 0.05$). In contrast, dividend payout showcased a positive yet statistically insignificant association with firm performance, represented by ($\beta=0.015$; $p=0.076 > 0.05$). The outcomes of this study yield a plethora of practical recommendations and policy considerations that merit in-depth exploration. To initiate, enterprises stand to gain substantial insights by engaging in a meticulous evaluation of their dividend disbursement strategies, particularly in light of the observed positive correlation between dividend payout and

Firm Performance. Undertaking an intensive scrutiny of the ramifications of incremental dividend distributions could potentially pave the way for companies to fine-tune their financial performance. Further research is imperative due to the varying impacts observed in this study. Deeper exploration into the underlying mechanisms can provide a more nuanced understanding of the relationships and potential causalities involved.

Keywords: Dividend Policy, Performance of Firms, Nairobi Securities Exchange

Introduction

Dividends are earnings (past or present) in real assets that are distributed among the shareholders of a firm in proportion to their ownership (Frankfurter & Wood, 2003). The shareholders of a firm expect a regular payback from their investment in form of a dividend. The dividend payout is defined by management upon which it becomes the basis of deciding whether or not to pay dividends and how hence the dividend policy of the firm.

The dividend policy of a firm provides substantial steps relating to dividend payment. Zelalem (2021) posit that companies follow legal procedures guiding the declaration of dividends. The management guides the company on the proportion distributable to shareowners in dividends form. Moreover, critical decisions on the re-investment by ploughing back is incorporated in the decision-making process. The dividend policy has been subjected to various debates on their relevance and irrelevance in the decision making. The management is driven by the continuous improvement of shareholders' wealth. Additionally, the amount to re-invest, distribute or speculate for investment opportunities guides the governance on the dividend policies (Migwi, 2015).

Policy of dividend blueprints, the strategies useful in business regarding dividend payments (Yohannes, 2016). Moreover, it guides the company towards stability without impairing the business capital. The state of a firm such as age, firm cycle and demands for re-investment direct the management on the policies formulation (Tesfaye, 2017). Moreover, the establishment of policies portrays the strength and the value of the company, gain goodwill from the investors and confidence from the shareholders. The policies have been utilized globally to set standard direction for specific company, boost credibility and build confidence among the shareholder. Dividend policy has been measured using ratio of dividend paid to earnings and market value (Nduta, 2016) and as such dividend policy enhances the fairness and equity in the distribution of dividends Cheptoo (2018).

The dividend policies have experienced tremendous changes over time. Tesfaye (2017) coined those different stages of business demands for differing proportion of payment. However, the start-up and growth stage may demand aggregate re-investment without payment of dividends (Chepkirui, 2021). Adugna, Mhret and Kumar (2020) quality use of bank size, inflation and liquidity to inform on the policies and dividend payment. The strong policies balance the interest of the shareholders. This is possible through the optimization of the shareholders' worth. In a nutshell, it creates an integral game plan for the business undertakings.

Research Problem

Dividend policy and firm performance have been studied and various observations have been made. One such observation is by Modigliani and Miller (1961) which gives a statement that under certain conditions, the profit strategy and dividend payment are immaterial. Whereas the dividend policies are integral in the entities' financial performance (Migwi, 2015), the profit strategies and dividend payment have been combined to enhance the development of dividend payout (Nduta, 2016). La Porta et al. (2016) observes that legal framework offers guidelines to the dividend payment.

A study done by Nissim and Ziv (2015) across 33 countries showed that the changes in dividend resulted from registered changes in earnings. Zhang (2015) analyzed the context of Japan and Australia and emphasized the importance of policies in directing the business undertaking towards the right direction. The desires and interest of organization are protected through prudent utilization of resources to realize the objective of value maximization. Baker et al. (2016) notes that proper dividend payment records plays an integral role in the stipulation of policies. The studies done globally have portrayed different findings due to the variance in their development, economic and sociopolitical state. Therefore, a local study bridges the contextual gaps.

Studies carried out in the emerging markets for instance Muiruri (2018) stated that the development of sound dividend policy is meant to guide the business re-investment and pay back to the shareholders. Nduta (2016)

depicted that the timing of dividend payout was positively correlated with the performance while Mwendwa (2021) concluded that profitability was immaterial in dividend payment. Fair enough Cheptoo (2018) indicated that an increment in the profitability caused an increase in the dividend payout therefore recommended the policies that state the proportion and ratio of re-investment and payout. The local studies have presented different ideas and perspectives causing mixed findings.

It suffices to note that both local and international research portrayed that dividend policies and the firms' performance have been linked though inconclusively. The standout has been witnessed on the payout and re-investment which many scholars have recommended for the policies (Muiruri, 2018). Nissim and Ziv (2015) delineated that an increase in earnings can translate to proportional increase in the dividend payout. La Porta et al (2016) concluded that strict policies in the dividend payment should be put in place. While this is applicable in developing countries, the same has not been well anchored in the emerging markets. It is imperative to substantiate that the effect of dividend policy on a firm's performance is puzzling and local study that seeks to converge these findings would be necessary.

The studies have demonstrated significantly that it varies depending on the policies formulated, country of operation and the approach in which the dividend payment is made. This shows that the researchers have a huge space to explore. Previous studies conducted in particular security markets in developed countries like Japan and Australia have not been fully utilized by local researchers. While some studies have focused on shareholder's value maximization and hence higher dividend payout, the effect of dividend policy on firm's performance have not been fully considered. This study therefore seeks answers to the question as to whether dividend policy affects the performance of a firm are inconclusive and therefore this study demonstrates the effect of dividend policy on firm performance by bringing together the investor, the management and the local framework using the firms listed at NSE. The objective of this research was to assess the effect of dividend policy on the firm's performance using the entities listed in the Nairobi Securities Exchange.

Literature Review

Agency Theory

In 1976, Jensen and Meckling embedded agency theory by attempting to intensify the separation of powers. In this theory the management and ownership have to be separated to ensure the effectiveness, transparency and accountability. Agency give powers to the management to act on behalf of principal. The shareholders are passive and expect the management to boost the utilization of resources to boost the value and reap the optimum benefits. Agency encourage the competence-based management and utmost integrity in the discharge of the organizational mandate.

Empirically, Kipkirui (2020) blueprinted the significant milestone from the agency theory. Mwendwa that agency theory blueprints the bold parameters for the corporate decision making concerning the dividend policy and dividend payments. Uwuigbe, Jafaru and Ajayi (2012) elucidated the crucial of agency in driving the business forward. Yohannes (2016) recommended the management to pursuit the mandates of the shareholders. Kipkirui and Omagwa (2021) exemplify that shareholders expected effectiveness and efficiency while reinforcing the firm's value.

The theory is relevant to the research since it prioritizes the formulation of policies by the management to steer the business forward. Moreover, it boosts the elimination of self-interest resulting in severe consequences to the management. It is supreme in the invaluable guidance to the operation, productivity and effectiveness of the organization to realize quality performance. Agency theory have received numerous criticism. Kipkirui (2020) indicated that the advocacy for balance-check measures raise the cost of operation hence reducing the benefits to the shareholders. Moreover, the presence of monitoring, evaluation, auditing and even authorization team can act as the bottleneck and predicament to the logistic and systematic flow (Kipkirui 2020). Agency cost is expensive mechanisms that take away a lion's share of the amount that can either be distributed as dividend or re-invested in the projects with positive NPV (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Signaling Theory

The hypothesis was set forth by Spence (1973) to dissect the presence of two parties that have different information about the firm. The management have greater access to credible and accurate information compared to the investors. The prevailing informational asymmetries results from the failure of the corporate management to relay the full information to the shareholders. The announcement regarding the dividend payout can trigger the changes in the stock market. The increment in the profitability portrays a quality management and highly reputable company.

Signaling theory has been useful in illustration of informational asymmetries. Chepkirui (2021) opined that a decrease in payment of dividend triggers the decrease in the merchandise prices hence translating to the reduction in the anticipated returns and vice versa. Scott (2015) encapsulated the critical role of access and control of information. Despite the technological innovation and mandatory disclosures, management still possess more details about the organization (Zelalem, 2021). However, Quraishi and Mahtab (2014) illustrated presence of information may not receive maximum consideration, utilization and execution.

The drawbacks of the theory include; the failure of the theory to anticipate the market trends and changes in the principal's tastes and preference. Moreover, the current presence of many players in the markets such as financial analysts and investment analysts have continuously developed fundamental and technical analysis to overcome the informational asymmetries. Furthermore, the new paradigm shifts, transparency, accountability and investors participation have reduced the informational gaps. They failed to substantiate the presence of abnormality and verse findings regarding the profitability and leverage (Syamuddih, 2011).

The theory is relevant because the managers have quality and credible information more than the principals of the firms. Moreover, the management utilizes the information to drive their agenda, source more funding and promote the reputation of the company. The management utilizes the theory in case of business decline to increase dividend payout and attract more investors. However, in reality the business might be struggling to clear their obligations (Scott, 2015).

Dividend Irrelevance Theory

The theory was developed by Miller and Modigliani (1961) while examining the dividend irrelevance. The epicenter of the study was imperfects market characterized by the tax-free. It coined out the presupposition that dividend payment would not increase the measure of the goods price in contrary it reduces the money available for re-investment in the business. The preposition includes no transactional related cost in the conversion of stocks, the decisions about the firms and have no effect dividend payout. In reality all the assumption may not stand the test of time.

The theory fails to elaborate on the risk and return aggregating from the absence of transaction and floatation cost. It delineates that dividend payment is immaterial in the addition of value to the stock price yet the dividend payment announcement does affect the stock price (Mwendwa, 2021). The absence of taxation may not be applicable to the developing nations who depend on dividend to increase their operations.

The theories give a chief latitude the dividend irrelevance in decision making (Zelalem, 2021). Moreover, Mutie (2011) explains that dividend payment decision is guided by the amount available for either business growth or shareholder's pay back. Zelalem (2021) dividend is a one of the payback method to the shareholder. The shareholders seek for the value addition to their company worthiness. It is imperative to state that dividend payment is useful in portraying the company's capabilities to generate revenue enough for apportionment towards re-investment and dividend payout. Zameer, Rasool, Iqbal and Arshad (2013) stipulated that the core objective of the organization is to reinforce the shareholders' value and this amount should translate to payment of dividend.

This theory is appropriate study in enhancing the entity's capability. It addresses the presence of asymmetric information in the dividend policies. The dividend payment reduces the amount that can be re-invested to gain future advantage. In summary, dividend irrelevance theory enhances the development of quality policies to promote the business. Miller and Modigliani (1961) postulates that company's value is influenced by basic

earning autonomy and risk. The drawbacks include the assumptions that all the investors are rational, absence of transaction and the floatation cost.

Empirical Literature Review

Globally, Ahmad, Barros and Sarmiento (2018) assessed the determinants of dividend policy. The research pivotal areas were Euronext Companies. The research availed OLS Regression to enhance the study. The driving force towards the investigation was controversial information regarding policies and payment of dividend. Moreover, the dividend policy was prioritized in the decision making by the corporate governance despite uneven pattern in dividend payment. The findings indicated that dividend yield translated to positive association with the DPO.

Furthermore, Ajanthan (2013) explored the association between dividend payout and the profitability. The study was undertaken in Sri-Lanka focusing on the listed Restaurants in the Colombo Stock Exchange. The study period was 5years and concluded that DPO affected the performance of the restaurant's firm positively and significantly.

Additionally, Ahmad, Barros and Sarmiento (2018) collected the data from 2007-2016 regarding the casual factors of dividend policy for the organization in Euronext 100. The dividend was utilized in the measurement of dividend policy. The OLS regression promoted analysis to find out the association. The study indicated that positive valuation was positively reflected on dividend. The study advocated for a stable dividend payout to eliminate the predicaments.

Empirically, Uwuigbe, Jafaru and Ajayi (2012) studied the divided policy in as regards the performance of listed firms. The key areas of consideration were structure, firm size and DPO. The study was undertaken in a period of 5years ranging from 2006-2010. A sample of 50 companies were obtained in the fact-finding process. The size of the firm and ownership structure registered a significant influence on the DPO.

Marekefu and Ouma (2012) analyzed the association between DPO and performance at NSE for the period from 2002 to 2010. An aggregate of 41 companies were incorporated as the sample and a regression analysis on the association was done. The findings were that DPO influenced the performance. The study emphasizes the crucial part played by the dividend policy to boost the investment and returns.

In addition, Thuraira (2014) examined the effect of retained earnings on the stock returns. The data covered a period of 5years with an interval of 2009 to 2013. The study optimized the regression model to elaborate on the study. The conclusion stated that retained earnings were immaterial in the stock returns. The study outcomes were contradictory to preceding studies by opining insignificant and inverse correlation.

A study by Murimi (2021) analyzed the dividend policy and the performance. It analyzed the insurance firms in Kenya. The researcher sourced the secondary that spanned from 2013-2018. Additionally, SPSS enhance the quantification and the computation. The findings indicated that DPO affected the performance of insurance. Moreover, retained earning registered a constructive impact on the financial performance. Researcher advocated for development and formulation of robust and quality policies.

According to Nduta (2016) established correlation between dividend policy and performance. It utilized 42 firms listed at NSE in the fact-finding process. The research period run from 2006-2015 while adopting the descriptive design. The findings summarized on the positive association among the three variables; DPO, dividend payment and firm size with performance. Nonetheless, the study postulated a negative association amid the leverage and performance. The current study seeks to bridge the conceptual, contextual and methodological gaps.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is master plan pertaining shaping the imagination on the predictor and the predicted variables (Kothari, 2015). It shows the association among the independent variables and in conjunction with the regressed variable. The research also elaborates the study of dividend policies and the firm's performance. Consequently, the dividend payout ratio, company earning and leverage are the regressor variables. Firm size is the intervening variable while the firm performance is regressed variable.

Independent Variable**Dividend Policy****Dependent variable****Firm Performance****Intervening Variable****Research Methodology**

Mugenda and Mugenda (2010) described research design as the overarching framework chosen to integrate the various elements of the research in a systematic manner to address problems. The research design supported the research question and problem through the utilization of a descriptive research design. It elucidated the relationship between the explanatory and explained variables. Kothari (2015) further detailed that the design provides a comprehensive plan guiding the research work, encompassing essential components to conclude the process of fact-finding. The study aimed to deduce cause-effect relationships.

As outlined by Cooper and Schindler (2014), the research design elucidated the research's intent. It facilitated a systematic process aligned with research problems, guided the analysis for precise and credible results, and identified the pertinent factors required to influence, elucidate, and infer associations. In order to address the existing knowledge gap, the empirical investigation delineated data collection, processes, measurement, examination, and analysis, progressing from hypothesis formulation to application and ultimately concluding the investigation (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

Mugenda and Mugenda (1999) represented the population as the set of elements, objects, and individuals selected for assessment. The firms listed at the NSE constituted the target population. The population consisted of 63 firms listed at the NSE, spanning from 2017 to 2021, and this sample size was considered sufficient for drawing inferences, as outlined in Appendix I. The chosen study period provided ample data for comprehensive conclusions. The population encompassed elements, objects, and individuals that shared similar characteristics

(Mugenda, 2010). In summary, the population enhanced the comprehension of companies falling under a single regulatory body, operating within similar parameters, and possessing common traits. Data collected was processed and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS version 25.

Analytical model was integral for providing the multiple linearity among the variables. It strived to provide the association between the explained and the explanatory variables. It enhanced the parameters optimized in the computation and quantification of data. This can be summarized as;

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Whereby:

Y= Financial Performance (Measured by ROA)

α_0 =y intercept of the regression (constant variable)

X_1 = Dividend Payout Ratio (DPS divided by EPS)

X_2 = Company Earning (Natural log of EBIT)

X_3 = Leverage (Equity Ratio as per Depth measured)

X_4 = Size (measured as natural log of sales)

ε = error term

Findings and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

It is pre-eminence to emphasize that the articulate presentation of the dataset is underscored by descriptive computations. Hence, the descriptive calculation aided in elucidating the characteristics of the dataset considered in the study. This process illustrates the condensed and graphical representation of data pertaining to specific variables integrated into the assessment. Indeed, it serves as a pathway for deducing the data's arrangement, spanning from mean to extreme values. Furthermore, it shapes the configuration of the dataset, shedding light on the discourse concerning the variable employed in the inquiry. To sum up, it encapsulates the measure of standard deviation, thereby elaborating on the extent of variability.

Descriptive statistics depicted the inherent qualities and attributes of the dataset pertaining to a specific variable. The data was gathered over the timeframe spanning from 2018 to 2022, as evident in the table provided below. During this interval, the performance of firms displayed a minimum value of 0.1527 and a maximum value of 0.3765. The mean for this metric stood at 0.2890, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.0432. This signified that over the five-year duration, the average firm size was 0.9417, with the highest value reaching 2.4627 and the lowest value representing an outlier at 0.0009.

The results also indicated that the least recorded value for company earnings was 0.9910, while the maximum reached 1.7739, yielding an average of 0.09435. Over the same period, the metric of leverage demonstrated an average of 2.4200 and a standard deviation of 0.2894. This implies that the range of dividend payout during this period exhibited a broad spectrum, with the highest and lowest values recorded at 0.001 and 1.5011 respectively. The dividend payout across the years 2018 to 2022 for these firms yielded an average of 0.1392 and a standard deviation of 0.2123.

After a meticulous inspection and comprehensive examination, it is noteworthy to mention that the data exhibited no significant anomalies. Furthermore, a rapid assessment of the standard deviation for firm performance yielded a value of 0.0432, making it the lowest among the various variables. Nonetheless, firm size yielded a value of 0.6343, while company earnings were denoted by 0.11093, leverage was indicated at 1.5039, and finally, dividend payout was represented by 0.2123. Considering the standard deviation values in relation to the corresponding averages, it can be inferred that there was minimal variability present, thus indicating the dataset's suitability for predictive analysis.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Firm Performance	315	.1527	.3765	.289037	.0431707

Firm Size	315	.0009	2.4627	.941713	.6342626
Company Earnings	315	.9910	1.7739	1.049533	.1109341
Leverage	315	1.5939	2.9491	2.420086	.2894344
Dividend Payout	315	.0001	1.5011	.139297	.2122594
Valid N (listwise)	315				

Correlation Analysis

This rigorous endeavor was prominent and pivotal in yielding precision of associations. Its integration stemmed from its pronounced significance in identifying obstacles and warranting extensive, intricate analyses (Nobanee & Dilshad, 2021). Moreover, it enhances the precision of relationships and deepens the apprehending of their magnitudes (Cooper & Schindle, 2014). The researcher executed a comprehensive correlation analysis among the variables under scrutiny in this study: firm size, company earnings, leverage, dividend payout, and firm performance. The Pearson correlation matrix was employed for this purpose. As a result, the correlation findings spanned from strongly positive to negative associations. The outcomes illustrate that firm size and company earnings exhibited an adverse correlation ($r=-0.185$ and $r=-0.477$, respectively) in relation to financial performance. Conversely, leverage and dividend payout showcased positive correlations with the dependent variable FP. Both leverage and dividend payout demonstrated substantial and moderate positive correlations, with values of $r=0.716$ and $r=0.180$, respectively, concerning the explained variable Firm performance.

Table 2 Correlation Analysis

		Correlations				
		Firm Performance	Firm Size	Company Earnings	Leverage	Dividend Payout
Firm Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	-.185**	-.477**	.716**	.180**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.000	.000	.001
	N	315	315	315	315	315
Firm Size	Pearson Correlation	-.185**	1	.000	-.400**	-.253**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		.994	.000	.000
	N	315	315	315	315	315
Company Earnings	Pearson Correlation	-.477**	.000	1	-.385**	.224**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.994		.000	.000
	N	315	315	315	315	315
Leverage	Pearson Correlation	.716**	-.400**	-.385**	1	.290**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	315	315	315	315	315
Dividend Payout	Pearson Correlation	.180**	-.253**	.224**	.290**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000	.000	
	N	315	315	315	315	315

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression Analysis

The execution of this regression computation carried a distinctive mandate in ascertaining the prevailing relationships. Consequently, it encompassed the numerical assessment of the dataset to illustrate both the direction and magnitude of these associations. The researcher expedited the regression analysis to establish the extent of correlation among the variables and to quantify the percentage of the correlation coefficient. Alongside addressing collinearity, the study formulated a mathematical model, crucial for projecting the future firm performance among the entities listed at NSE, with a primary emphasis on the predictor variables mentioned earlier.

Model summary

The model summary presented beneath portrays an R-value of 0.755, indicating a substantial correlation of 75.5% among the variables examined in this investigation. The R-Square value, denoting the correlation coefficient, communicates that 57.1% of the variances observed in firm performance concerning the dividend policy for firms listed on the NSE can be ascribed to firm performance, company earnings, firm size, and

leverage. The remaining 42.9% of fluctuations in financial performance arise from factors not encompassed in this assessment.

Table 3 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.755 ^a	.571	.565	.0284742	.530

a. Predictors: (Constant), Dividend Payout, Company Earnings, Firm Size, Leverage

b. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

ANOVA

This test is pivotal in elucidation of differences in the averages among many groupings. The ANOVA table in the regression findings delineates an F-Statistics of 102.946 and significance of 0.000. The outcome was widened and deepened by affirmation of the sum of squared regression as 0.334 and mean squared as 0.083 with 4 degrees of freedom while, sum of square residual is 0.251 and 0.001 mean square with 310 degrees of freedom. As a result, the outcome exemplifies that the model was statistically significant since the significance value 0.000 beneath the P-Value of 0.05.

Table 4 Analysis of Variance

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.334	4	.083	102.946	.000 ^b
	Residual	.251	310	.001		
	Total	.585	314			

a. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Dividend Payout, Company Earnings, Firm Size, Leverage

Regression Coefficients

Researcher harnessed the unstandardized coefficients in column B to construct the mathematical model. As a consequence, evidences underscore that, while holding all factors constant, the impact of the predictors variables on firm performance amounts to 0.155. Furthermore, the conclusions unveil that firm size establishes a constructive and notable rapport with firm performance ($\beta=0.006$; $p=0.036 < 0.05$). Delving deeper, computation illuminates that company earnings elicit a detrimental and marked connection with Firm Performance (the regressed variable) ($\beta=-0.098$; $p=0.000 < 0.05$). The data presented in section 4.7 also illustrates that leverage forges a positive and substantial link with firm performance, as manifested by ($\beta=0.094$; $p=0.000 < 0.05$). In contrast, dividend payout showcases a positive yet statistically material tie to firm performance, as indicated by ($\beta=0.015$; $p=0.076 > 0.05$).

Table 5 Coefficients^a of Determination

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.155	.031		5.022	.000
	Firm Size	.006	.003	.087	2.108	.036
	Company Earnings	-.098	.017	-.251	-5.696	.000
	Leverage	.094	.007	.633	13.246	.000
	Dividend Payout	.015	.009	.075	1.781	.076

With the above findings, researchers generated a mathematical model as

$$Y = 0.155 + 0.006 X_1 - 0.098 X_2 + 0.094 X_3 + 0.015 X_4 + \epsilon$$

This establishes that the autonomous value is notably positive at 0.155, signifying that whenever all variables associated with dividend policy remain unaltered, the firm performance experiences a positive shift of 0.155. As

a result, a single unit increase in firm size leads to a substantial 0.6% augmentation in firm performance, maintaining all other influencing factors constant. Furthermore, a marginal change of one unit in company earnings results in a relatively insignificant 9.8% decline in firm performance, while keeping other determinants constant. However, an isolated unitary rise in leverage corresponds to a significant 9.4% surge in firm performance under the condition of constant enablers. Spearheading this thread of analysis, the addition of a solitary unit in dividend payout holds pivotal significance, triggering a 1.5% upswing in firm performance. This transformation occurs exclusively when all other contributing factors are held steadfast.

Recognizing the profound implications of these significant findings, it is essential to underscore that a comprehensive and definitive conclusion can be effectively elucidated by:

$$Y = -0.155 + 0.006 X_1 - 0.098 X_2 + 0.094 X_3 + \varepsilon$$

This is because the other one variable is insignificant

Whereby

Y = Firm Performance

A₀ = y intercept of the regression (constant variable)

X₁ = Firm Size

X₂ = Company Earnings

X₃ = Leverage

X₄ = Dividend Payout

ε = error term

Discussion of the Findings

The outcomes detailed within the model summary established that the quartet of regressor variables accounted for 57.1% of the variance observed in the financial performance of the selected firms. This underscored that 42.9% of the fluctuations in financial performance were attributed to additional determinants not encompassed in the model. Expanding this analysis, the ANOVA test asserted that the model held significance and practicality in forecasting the firm performance of the companies, as evidenced by the F-statistics of 102.946 (p < 0.05).

In the quest to comprehensively understand the interplay between various factors and firm performance, the researcher harnessed the power of unstandardized coefficients from column B to formulate a mathematical model. This model revealed that under constant conditions, the effect of the listed independent variables on firm performance is quantified at 0.155. This pivotal insight, echoed by other studies, forms a foundation for the subsequent analyses.

Expanding on this, it is noteworthy that firm size emerged as a dynamic variable, showcasing a positive and significant relationship with firm performance ($\beta = 0.006$; $p = 0.036 < 0.05$). Ibhagui and Olokoyo (2018) support this perspective with their findings of a positive interrelationship, while Chang (2018) contrasts it by suggesting a negative interrelationship between firm size and performance.

Delving further, the intricate impact of company earnings on firm performance was unraveled, revealing a notable negative relationship ($\beta = -0.098$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). This alignment with the findings of Vibhakar, Tripathi, Johari, and Jha (2023) underscores the instrumental role of company earnings in determining financial performance. However, a divergent narrative arises from Chakroun, Ben Amar, and Ben Amar (2022), as well as Almashhadani and Almashhadani (2022), who highlight a negative impact attributed to earnings management. Counterbalancing these viewpoints, Kalbuana, Suryati, and Pertiwi (2022) advocate for a positive interconnection between earnings management and firm performance.

Moreover, as the analysis unfolded, the spotlight turned to the influence of leverage on firm performance. The results concretely established a positive and significant relationship ($\beta = 0.094$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Das, Chowdhury, and Islam (2022) steer the conversation by postulating a negative effect of leverage on firm performance, while Jatoi and Rasheed (2023) introduce a counter perspective by demonstrating a positive relationship.

Lastly, the relationship between dividend payout and firm performance was scrutinized, revealing a positive yet insignificant connection ($\beta=0.015$; $p=0.076>0.05$). The findings align with Ukpong and Ukpe (2023), who assert a material and significant positive impact of dividend payout on firm performance. Conversely, Basdekis, Christopoulos, Gakias, and Katsampoxakis (2023) present a different facet, concluding that dividend payout can have a detrimental effect on firm performance. In essence, this comprehensive analysis, alongside the juxtaposition with a plethora of international studies, adds layers of insight to the complex puzzle of firm performance, offering a more nuanced and holistic understanding of the intricate relationships that underpin it. The findings of this investigation were derived from a dataset originating from a population demonstrating normal distribution. This was evident from the alignment of data points along the linear trend depicted in the Q-Q plots of individual variables. Furthermore, the diagnostic analysis indicated the absence of multicollinearity issues among the independent variables. To elaborate, the tolerance values for firm size, company earnings, leverage, and dividend payout, namely 0.805, 0.716, 0.607, and 0.776, respectively, surpassed the threshold of 0.2, confirming that these variables did not suffer from multicollinearity concerns. In addition, the tolerance values of 1.242, 1.398, 1.648, and 1.289, respectively, were all well below the threshold of 10, further confirming the absence of multicollinearity among the independent variables. This robust diagnostic analysis ensures the reliability of the results obtained.

Conclusions

Compiled dataset was sourced from expeditiously sourced from published, and audited data extracted from reputable institutions such as KNBS, CBK, and NSE. The pivotal jurisdictions of CMA in data generation cannot be overstated. The extensive dataset underwent a rigorous process of broad-spectrum review, painstaking editing, and thorough completion, followed by assiduous categorization using SPSS. This meticulous procedure paved the way for both descriptive and inferential computations, undertaken with precision and diligence.

In juxtaposition to the previous comprehensive investigation, it can be encapsulated that this current study stands as a pinnacle in providing heightened illumination. A panoramic view unfolds, depicting the intricate nexus between dividend policies and firm performance. Ahmad, Barros & Sarmiento (2018) embarked on an exploration of the Euronext Companies landscape, unraveling a positive nexus between dividend yield and DPO. This sentiment resonates with Ajanthan (2013), who delved into the realm of Sri Lankan restaurants, revealing the advantageous impact of DPO on performance. Uwuigbe et al. (2012) traversed the terrain of Nigerian firms, revealing the influence of firm size and ownership on DPO. Drawing parallels with these inquiries, Sasu, Abor, and Osei (2017) underscored the positive links between DPS and shareholder value in Ghana, while also acknowledging the contrasting negative correlation with dividend yield.

Steering into a different lane, Yemi and Seriki (2018) navigated the domain of retained earnings' effect on performance and market value. Meanwhile, Marekefu and Ouma (2012) acknowledged the imprint of DPO on NSE performance. Empowered by insights from these antecedent studies, the current research harnessed unstandardized coefficients from column B to construct a mathematical model. This model unveiled that under unvarying conditions, the cumulative impact of the enumerated independent variables on firm performance amounted to 0.155.

Recommendations

The outcomes of this study yield a plethora of practical recommendations and policy considerations that merit in-depth exploration. To initiate, enterprises stand to gain substantial insights by engaging in a meticulous evaluation of their dividend disbursement strategies, particularly in light of the observed positive correlation between dividend payout and Firm Performance. Undertaking a comprehensive scrutiny of the ramifications of incremental dividend distributions could potentially pave the way for companies to fine-tune their financial performance.

Moreover, the study underscores the pivotal role that firm size assumes in sculpting Firm Performance. Consequently, establishments might strategically orient their endeavors toward growth initiatives aimed at augmenting their size. Nonetheless, the execution of such strategies demands a nuanced comprehension of the intricate interplay among variables. This strategic awareness is pivotal to forestall unintended repercussions that might arise from embarking on size expansion initiatives without a comprehensive grasp of their multifaceted implications.

It is worth underscoring the imperative for a sense of prudence when navigating the domain of company earnings, particularly given the research's unveiling of an adverse relationship with Firm Performance. This underscores the crucial significance of astute financial management practices and the cultivation of sustainable earnings strategies. Such meticulous practices are not only integral to safeguarding overall performance but also harbor the potential to elevate it.

Interestingly, the study unveils the salutary impact of leverage on Firm Performance. This revelation prompts companies to contemplate delving into avenues of strategic debt management and financing. By adroitly capitalizing on their capital structure, enterprises could unlock pathways that potentially lead to advantageous financial outcomes.

Although the study points to an insignificant relationship between dividend payout and Firm Performance, it becomes paramount for organizations to embrace a holistic vantage point when sculpting their dividend policies. The imperative lies in taking into account factors that extend beyond mere financial metrics, encompassing elements such as investor expectations and the dynamic landscape of the market. Collectively, these multifarious facets should inform the conception and execution of dividend policies, ensuring their alignment with broader organizational objectives.

Regarding practical implementation, organizations should establish a routine of consistently assessing and adjusting their dividend strategies in direct response to evolving economic circumstances, industry trends, and their individual financial standings. Furthermore, as they apply the insights gleaned from this study, companies must take into account the precise operational context, industry dynamics, and distinctive market characteristics. It's imperative to acknowledge that a customized approach is paramount, given that a universal solution is not applicable.

Moreover, the incorporation of risk management tactics into decision-making protocols is vital for preemptively managing potential adverse effects, particularly in relation to company earnings. Ultimately, corporations should embrace a forward-thinking perspective and align their tactics with overarching business aspirations, ensuring enduring growth and sustained performance over the long run. In summation, the study's findings furnish invaluable direction to enterprises and policymakers alike, equipping them with informed tools for making decisions concerning dividend policy, firm size, company earnings, and leverage. Nonetheless, the prosperous execution of these recommendations' hinges on their seamless alignment with the distinct circumstances and objectives of each organization.

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